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Tobacco packaging and labeling policies in the WHO African Region: Progress 15 years after adoption of the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control Article 11 Implementation Guidelines

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Article 11 of the World Health Organization's Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (WHO FCTC) requires Parties to adopt and implement effective tobacco packaging and labeling policies to communicate health risks and reduce tobacco consumption. The goal of this study was to assess adoption of these policies in the WHO African Region (AFRO).

Methods: We reviewed tobacco packaging and labeling policies adopted in AFRO from the Campaign for Tobacco-Free Kids' Tobacco Control Laws database (www.tobaccocontrolaws.org). We assessed these policies based on WHO FCTC Article 11 and its Implementation Guidelines examining three sub-policy areas (health warning labels [HWLs], descriptive constituents and emissions information, and misleading packaging and labeling). We developed a scoring system to rank AFRO countries individually and by World Bank's income-level groups and documented the progress during 1985-2023.

Results: Forty (of 47) AFRO countries adopted national laws, of which a majority adopted large rotating pictorial HWLs and banned misleading descriptors; only Cote d'Ivoire and Mauritius adopted standardized packaging. The higher a country is in the World Bank's income-level group, the stronger their packaging and labeling policies are. This observation was not present in the sub-policy area of HWLs. Prior to approving the WHO FCTC Article 11 Implementation Guidelines, only 23 countries adopted text-only HWLs whereas 26 countries adopted pictorial HWLs after the approval.

Conclusion: Several AFRO countries have adopted tobacco packaging and labeling policies that align with the WHO FCTC Article 11 Implementation Guidelines. More efforts could be directed toward the low-income group and disseminating standardized packaging throughout AFRO.

IMPLICATIONS

In the WHO African Region (AFRO), the number of tobacco users is increasing, highlighting the need for tobacco packaging and labeling policies aligned with WHO FCTC Article 11 and its Implementation Guidelines as these are proven tobacco control strategies. This study provides a country-level and income-level group ranking of tobacco packaging and labeling policies and documents the evolution of health warning labels adopted in AFRO. It also identifies regional and income-level group successes and gaps in tobacco product packaging and labeling policies and provides recommendations to further align with WHO FCTC Article 11 and its Implementation Guidelines.

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3 Tobacco use is the leading cause of preventable death, costs the global economy US \$1.4
4 trillion annually, and causes 8 million tobacco-related deaths each year.[1,2] Though the World
5 Health Organization (WHO)'s African Region (AFRO) currently has the lowest smoking
6 prevalence among the six WHO regions, the WHO projects the number of adult smokers in
7 AFRO to increase by 3 million (48 to 51 million) by 2025 based on 2000 levels.[3,4] Estimated
8 tobacco use rates among adults in the AFRO region in 2020 was 10.3% (36.7% males, 7.8%
9 females) and the estimated prevalence of smokeless tobacco use was 2.7% (3.8% males, 1.6%
10 females) in 2018 [3]. Projected increases in tobacco use has been attributed to the growth of
11 economies, the increasing presence of transnational tobacco companies in AFRO, and aggressive
12 tobacco marketing tactics, particularly among youth and women.[3,5,6,7]

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27 Of the 47 countries in AFRO, 45 are Party (all but Eritrea and South Sudan) to the WHO
28 Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (WHO FCTC). Under WHO FCTC Article 11,
29 Parties are required to adopt and implement effective measures to ensure that tobacco packaging
30 and labeling: is not false, misleading, or deceptive, includes large, rotating health warning labels
31 [HWLs] describing the harmful effects of tobacco use in the principal language(s) of the country;
32 and includes information on relevant constituents and emissions (C&E) information. The WHO
33 FCTC Article 11 Implementation Guidelines, adopted in 2008, assist Parties in meeting their
34 treaty obligations and increasing the effectiveness of their packaging and labeling measures.[8]
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36 For example, the guidelines confirm that HWL effectiveness increases with size and the
37 inclusion of pictures. In addition, the guidelines clarify that C&E information should be
38 descriptive and should not contain quantitative figures for emissions yields and urge Parties to
39 restrict or prohibit the use of logos, colors, and other promotional elements on packaging, instead
40 allowing only brand and product names in a standard font style and color (plain or standardized
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3 packaging). Large pictorial HWLs have been associated with increases in knowledge, quitline
4 calls, and reductions in smoking consumption and prevalence.[9]
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8 Studies in other regions (Americas[10] and South-East Asia[11]) have similarly assessed
9 countries' regulatory environments for HWL characteristics and their alignment with WHO
10 FCTC Article 11 and its Implementation Guidelines. Literature in the AFRO region has assessed
11 the effect of the WHO FCTC on the passage of HWL policies,[12] analysis of HWL size in the
12 region (2011),[13] and country-level analyses on implementation and adoption of HWL
13 policies.[14,15] In this study, we evaluate the adoption of tobacco product packaging and
14 labeling policies based on Article 11 of the WHO FCTC and its Implementation Guidelines in
15 AFRO as of December 2023 and compare the strength of policies adopted across World Bank's
16 income-level groups in the region.
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29 **METHODS**

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32 Between August 2022 and December 2023, we conducted secondary analysis of policies
33 regulating tobacco packaging and labeling in AFRO.
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36 *Data Collection*

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38 Data was extracted from Tobacco Control Laws (www.tobaccocontrollaws.org), a
39 database developed and regularly updated by lawyers from the International Legal Consortium at
40 the Campaign for Tobacco-Free Kids (CTFK), in collaboration with in-country lawyers. The
41 database consists of a repository of national tobacco control laws adopted globally accompanied
42 by detailed legal analysis of how a country's tobacco control policies compare to the WHO
43 FCTC.[16]
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3 Of the 47 AFRO countries, seven (Angola, Equatorial Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Lesotho,
4 Liberia, Malawi, and South Sudan) have not approved any tobacco packaging and labeling
5 policies. The other 40 countries have adopted different national laws and regulations. We
6 reviewed details about these laws and policies to summarize here. Details came from both the
7 database for 34 countries and from a review of policies in the repository that had not yet been
8 analyzed for the database for 6 countries (Botswana, Central African Republic, Mozambique,
9 Sao Tome and Principe, Zambia, and Zimbabwe). The analyses for these 6 countries were
10 completed by a lawyer from the ILC team and co-author of the paper (KD).
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22 *Data Analysis*

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25 We organized the packaging and labeling measures contained in Article 11 of the WHO
26 FCTC and its Implementation Guidelines into three sub-policy areas and then developed a
27 scoring system (a modified version created for the Americas [10]) to rank individual AFRO
28 countries and by income-level groups according to the adoption of 15 main measures: 1) tobacco
29 HWL features: type (text-only or pictorial), location (lateral only or front and back), size (as a
30 percentage of the pack PDAs: less than 30%, 30% to 49%, 50% to 69%, and 70% or more),
31 rotation period, number (single or multiple), principal language/s, message content areas (general
32 or specified), and quit resource information; 2) descriptive tobacco C&E information: message
33 (single or multiple), rotation period; and 3) misleading tobacco packaging and labeling: ban on
34 brand descriptors, ban on emission yields, ban on figures, colors, and symbols, ban on expiry
35 date, and plain packaging. The analysis applied to different types of tobacco products (i.e.,
36 smoked, and smokeless). The maximum score a country could achieve was 30 points. Countries
37 were ranked according to the total points they earned.
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3 For income-level analysis, we applied the World Bank's income-level classification into
4 4 groups: High income countries (HIC), upper-middle income countries (UMIC), lower-middle
5 income countries (LMIC), and low-income countries (LIC) to the WHO African Region. The
6 World Bank bases their income-level classifications on Gross National Income (GNI) per capita
7 of the previous year (2021).
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10 *Compliance status*

11 We also assessed AFRO countries' compliance with each one of the 15 main measures
12 based on requirements and recommendations of WHO FCTC Article 11 and its Implementation
13 Guidelines. Countries received one point for each of the measures they are in compliance with.
14 A country could achieve a total of 15 points.
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17 Finally, to illustrate the historical development of packaging and labeling and to highlight
18 the progress in AFRO over the years (1985 to 2023), we took into consideration HWLs' type
19 (text-only or pictorial) and size (as a percentage of the pack PDAs: less than 30%, 30% to 49%,
20 50% to 69%, and 70% or more).
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27 **RESULTS**

28 *Tobacco Health Warning Label Features*

29 Supplementary Table 1 provides an overview of tobacco HWL features according to the
30 type of tobacco product that requires a warning, the type, location and size of the warning, the
31 rotation system, number, message content, language, and cessation information.
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36 **Tobacco product type.** Six countries differentiate HWL requirements between smoked
37 and smokeless tobacco products. Cabo Verde and Mauritius require HWLs only for cigarettes;
38 Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) and Niger only for cigarettes and cigars; Gabon, Gambia,
39 Tanzania, and Uganda for all smoked tobacco products. Madagascar differentiates HWL
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3 requirements between cigarettes and snuff, and chewing tobacco. Twenty-five countries apply
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5 the same requirements to all tobacco products, including Togo that extend them to other nicotine
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7 products like e-cigarettes.
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10 **Type.** Text-only HWLs are required in 14 countries and a combination of pictorial and
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12 text in 26 countries. Madagascar is the only country whose requirements differ based on the type
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14 of tobacco product: pictorial HWLs for cigarettes and snuff and text-only for chewing tobacco.
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17 **Location.** Thirty-five countries require that HWLs are printed both on the front and back
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19 of smoked tobacco packaging. Four of those countries have an additional text-only HWL on the
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21 lateral side of the pack. Central African Republic requires HWLs only on the lateral side of
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23 smoked tobacco packaging. Congo, Sao Tome and Principe, Zambia, and Zimbabwe do not
24
25 specify the location.
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28 **Size.** Two countries require that HWLs cover less than 30% of the PDAs: South Africa
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30 20% for smoked and 7.5% for smokeless tobacco products; Mozambique 27.5% of the PDAs.
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32 Eight countries require that HWLs cover between 30-49% of the PDAs. Madagascar requires
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34 that HWLs cover 50% of cigarettes and snuff, but only 25% of chewing tobacco. Twelve
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36 countries require that HWLs cover 50-69% of the PDAs, and another 13 countries require a size
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38 of at least 70% of the PDAs. Benin, Mauritius, and Sierra Leone have the largest HWLs in the
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40 AFRO region at 90%. Six countries do not specify the size.
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45 **Rotation system.** Nineteen countries require rotation of HWLs on a scheduled basis.
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47 Twelve of these countries require rotation every two years, while six require an annual rotation.
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49 Mauritania requires HWL rotation on smoked tobacco (two years), but it is uncertain how often
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51 HWLs on smokeless tobacco must be rotated.
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3 **Number.** Only one warning message is required on all packages in nine countries.
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5 Eighteen countries require more than one message to be in rotation at a given time, ranging from
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7 two (Cameroon, Chad, Comoros, Gabon, Mauritania, Niger) to 13 (Sierra Leone). Kenya,
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9 Madagascar, Sierra Leone, and South Africa have different HWL number requirements for
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11 smoked and smokeless tobacco packs.
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15 **Message content.** Eight countries require a general message such as “Tobacco is
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17 dangerous to health.” Almost half require HWLs with themes related to specific health effects
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19 including different types of cancer, cardiovascular or respiratory diseases, problems during
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21 pregnancy, impotence, aging, rotten teeth, and death. Seven countries require warnings on
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23 addiction. Gambia is the only AFRO country that adopted the use of non-health messages, as
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25 recommended by Article 11 Implementation Guidelines, including the messages "Tobacco use
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27 leads to poverty”; “Smoking pollutes the environment”; and “Cigarette ash causes bush fires”.
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29 Mauritania and Nigeria also include a message encouraging quitting smoking. Only five
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31 countries require different health effect messages specifically for smokeless tobacco products.
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33 Ten countries do not specify the content of the messages.
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38 **Language.** Thirty-three countries require that HWLs messages be written in one or more
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40 principal languages.
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42 **Information for cessation.** Only Ghana and Senegal require a “quitline” number on all
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44 tobacco product packages.
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47 *Descriptive Constituents & Emissions Information*

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49 Supplementary Table 2 presents information on the size, location, rotation, number, and
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51 message content of C&E messages.
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3 **Size.** Uganda and South Africa are the only two AFRO countries that specify the size of
4 C&E messages required. Uganda requires that messages cover 100% of the top panel of tobacco
5 packaging. South Africa mandates 20% coverage of the lateral panels of smoked tobacco
6 products as part of one of the eight HWLs specified.
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11 **Location.** Eswatini, Gambia, Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria, Senegal, and Togo require C&E
12 messaging on the lateral side of packages. South Africa requires C&E messaging on the back of
13 the package, and Uganda on the top panel of the pack.
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19 **Rotation and number.** Gambia is the only country in AFRO to require rotation (every
20 two years) for C&E messages. Nigeria, South Africa, and Uganda require one message. Togo
21 requires two messages, and Ghana three different messages.
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26 **Message content.** Seven countries specify the content of C&E messaging. The most
27 common C&Es described are tar, nicotine, carbon monoxide, and other harmful chemicals.
28 Ghana, South Africa, and Togo reference specific chemicals that cause harm including cyanide
29 and arsenic. Additionally, Ghana, Togo, and Uganda include information on how these
30 chemicals may cause different types of cancers such as lung, skin, bladder, liver, and kidney.
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38 *Misleading Tobacco Packaging and Labeling*

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40 Supplementary Table 3 provides information on regulating misleading tobacco packaging
41 and labeling, including brand descriptors, emission yields, figures, colors, and other signs, expiry
42 date, and standardized or “plain” packaging.
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47 **Brand descriptors.** Brand descriptors that could imply less harm (including ‘light’,
48 ‘ultra-light’, ‘mild’, ‘low tar’, ‘smooth,’ ‘slim,’ etc.) are banned in 32 countries.
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3 **Emission yields.** The quantitative display of figures for emission yields (including tar,
4 CO, and nicotine) is banned in 14 countries. On the other hand, thirteen countries require the
5 display of figures for emission yields which contradicts Article 11 Implementation Guidelines.
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9 **Figures, colors, and other signs.** Figures, colors, and other signs on tobacco product
10 packaging is banned in 27 countries.
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14 **Expiry date.** Only Ethiopia and Mauritania ban the use of an expiry date on tobacco
15 product packaging. On the other hand, five countries (DRC, Gabon, Malawi, Niger, Nigeria)
16 require expiry dates which contradicts Article 11 Implementation Guidelines.
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20 **Standardized or “plain” packaging.** Cote d’Ivoire and Mauritius are the only two
21 countries in the AFRO region to require standardized or “plain” packaging. Botswana Tobacco
22 Control Act 2021 provides powers to introduce plain packaging of tobacco products. However,
23 as of December 2023, Botswana has not introduced plain packaging.
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26 27 28 29 30 31 *Individual and Income-Level Group Scoring and Ranking*

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33 Supplementary Tables 4 and 5 rank AFRO countries within each World Bank income-
34 level group based on the level of adoption of the requirements and recommendations of WHO
35 FCTC Article 11 and its Implementation Guidelines.
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39 Overall, the HIC group scored the highest (60%), though this includes only one AFRO
40 country: Seychelles. The UMIC (49%), LMIC (42%), and LIC (39%) groups follow. Seychelles
41 (18/30), Mauritius (24/30), Ghana (23/30), and Uganda (22/30) scored the highest in each of the
42 four income-level groups.
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46 Within the sub-policy area of HWLs, the UMIC group scored the highest out of the
47 maximum possible score (86%), followed by HIC (75%), LIC (52%), and LMIC (51%).
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3 Mauritius (15/16), Seychelles (12/16), Chad (15/16), and Ghana (15/16) scored the highest in
4 each income-level group respectively.
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7 Within the sub-policy area of C&Es, a different ranking occurred: the HIC group scored
8 the highest (50%) out of the maximum possible score followed by UMIC (25%), LMI (18%),
9 and LIC (18%). Namibia and South Africa (3/4), Ghana, Kenya, and Eswatini (3/4), and Uganda,
10 Gambia, and Togo (3/4) scored the highest in each income-level group respectively.
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16 Within the sub-policy area of misleading tobacco packaging and labeling, the HIC and
17 the UMIC group scored the highest (40%) out of the maximum possible score followed by LMIC
18 (35%) and LIC (26%). Mauritius (9/10), Mauritania (6/10), and Ethiopia (6/10) scored the
19 highest in each income-level group respectively.
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26 The classification of countries by income level suggests the higher the country is in the
27 World Bank income level group, the stronger their packaging and labeling policies are. This is
28 further supported when taking the mean score in each income level group: UMIC (14.8 points);
29 LMIC (12.5 points); LIC (11.8 points). By averaging the score in each income-level group, we
30 attempt to address the outliers in each category, which affects the total scores used for income
31 classification rankings. Note that this observation was not present in the sub-policy area of
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Compliance status

Supplementary Table 6 presents the ranking of AFRO countries based on the compliance with WHO FCTC's Article 11 requirements and recommendations. No AFRO country is in compliance with all 15 measures required and recommended by WHO FCTC Article 11 and its Implementation Guidelines. Ghana is in compliance with 13, being the highest in the region.

Historical Evolution of Warning Labels in AFRO

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Supplementary Table 7 presents the evolution of HWLs size and type in each AFRO country. Figures 1 and 2 show the number of countries per year from 1985 to 2023, by size category and type respectively. Figure 3 shows the number of countries per year from 1985 to 2023 with pictorial HWLs at least 50% of the PDAs. Considering the WHO FCTC Article 11 Guidelines on Packaging and Labelling of Tobacco Products adopted in November 2008, we demarcated two periods in the evolution of HWLs (pre- and post-Article 11 Implementation Guidelines):

Period I (1985 - Oct 2008):

This period starts in 1985 with the first AFRO country adopting a text-only HWLs on tobacco packages (Algeria, no size requirements). In almost 24 years, 23 countries adopted text-only HWLs. In 2003, Madagascar became the first to adopt text-only HWLs of 50% of the PDAs of tobacco packages, and with Cameroon were the only two of that size during this period. In 2007 Kenya became the first country to adopt pictorial HWLs. It is worth noting that, during this period, some multinational tobacco companies voluntarily placed text-only HWLs in English on the side of packs being exported to countries without mandatory HWLs, including countries in the AFRO region. In many of these countries, this voluntary action by the tobacco industry delayed the adoption of mandatory and stronger (i.e., larger, in the principal language) HWLs.[17]

Period II (Nov 2008- Dec 2023):

This period starts in late 2008 with the first AFRO country adopting a pictorial HWLs larger than 50% (Mauritius, 65%). In almost 16 years, 26 countries adopted pictorial HWLs. In 2013, Niger became the first country with pictorial HWLs covering 70% of PDAs. In 2022, Mauritius briefly adopted the largest warnings in AFRO and in the entire world, covering 95% of

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3 the PDAs; the law was modified soon after and the size was decreased to 90%. Mauritius also
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5 became the first AFRO country to adopt plain tobacco packaging.
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7 **DISCUSSION**

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10 A regional assessment of tobacco packaging and labeling policies in AFRO illustrates
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12 that important progress has occurred in the region, especially following the adoption of the WHO
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14 FCTC Article 11 Guidelines in 2008. Several countries in AFRO now align their tobacco control
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16 laws with Article 11 and its guidelines by requiring pictorial and textual HWLs covering at least
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18 50% of the PDAs on smoked and smokeless tobacco products packaging. The rate of adopting
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20 pictorial HWLs of at least 50% has also exponentially grown from one country prior to 2008 to
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22 24 as of December 2023 (Figure 3).
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26 This assessment also provides key takeaways for income-level classifications. The higher
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28 a country is on the World Bank income-level group, the closer it is to achieving WHO FCTC
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30 Article 11 compliance. While we cannot claim that the HIC group is a part of this pattern as it is
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32 comprised of only one country, all other groups fall within the claim. It is useful to identify areas
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34 that fall behind in adoption of HWL policies, so that appropriate advocacy efforts can be funded
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36 that target countries requiring further political action to achieve WHO FCTC Article 11
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38 compliance. Countries classified as LIC appear to require the most attention going forward.
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43 Most countries in AFRO (39/47) have adopted a law requiring HWLs, similar to the
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45 Americas (31/35) [10] and Southeast Asia (10/10)[11] regions. Of the countries that have
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47 adopted a law requiring HWLs, laws in AFRO require rotation less often (19/39, 49%) compared
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49 to countries in the Americas (34/31,77%)[10] and Southeast Asia (10/10, 100%).[11] Similar to
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51 the AFRO region, a majority of countries in the Americas and Southeast Asia specify the
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53 principal language and content of the messages, while only a few make a distinction in the
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3 message contents between smoked and smokeless tobacco products and require quit information
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5 on tobacco packaging (2/39, 5% in AFRO; 9/31, 29% in the Americas; 5/10, 50% in Southeast
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7 Asia). Fourteen (of 39, 36%) countries in the AFRO region require a descriptive message on
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9 C&E on at least one type of tobacco product, compared to 21/31 (68%) in the Americas[10] and
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11 8/10 (80%) in Southeast Asia.[11]
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15 Standardized packaging for tobacco products is the least adopted packaging and labeling
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17 policy in the region. Only two countries (Mauritius and Cote d'Ivoire) require standardized
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19 packaging for tobacco products in AFRO. The struggle to disseminate these best practices is also
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21 evident in the region of the Americas and Southeast Asia as only Canada and Uruguay and
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23 Thailand and Singapore have adopted standardized packaging in each region respectively.[10,11]
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25 Overall this is a growing concern in LMICs as only six LMICs compared to 18 HICs have
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27 adopted standardized packaging.[18] The adoption of standardized packaging has shown to
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29 reduce the appeal and attractiveness of tobacco packaging, especially among youth[19] and if
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31 adopted comprehensively, can potentially reduce the smoking prevalence.[20] The tobacco
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33 industry has responded by bringing legal challenges, particularly trade threats, against countries
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35 introducing standardized packaging, though so far, the tobacco industry has lost all of its legal
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37 claims. Anti-tobacco trade litigation funds, coordinated by CTFK, have been created to combat
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39 the tobacco industry's use of international trade and investment agreements in LMIC as an
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41 argument to prevent countries from adopting policies such as standardized packaging.
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47 The Campaign for Tobacco-Free Kids, supported by funding from the Bill and Melinda
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49 Gates Foundation, has provided technical assistance to adopt and implement tobacco control
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51 measures including package and labeling laws in several AFRO countries such as Botswana,
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53 Cameroon, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria, Senegal, and
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3 Uganda. Given the progress of adopting WHO FCTC-based tobacco packaging and labeling
4 policies in AFRO, future research should assess these policies as it pertains to emerging tobacco
5 and nicotine products such as electronic nicotine delivery systems, heated tobacco products, and
6 oral nicotine products, which are increasingly available in the region. Furthermore, given that
7 there are several LMICs in AFRO that generally have weaker institutions and lack resources to
8 properly monitor, implement and enforce tobacco control policies,[21,22] future research should
9 assess the implementation of these policies in AFRO to better understand their impact.
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19 This study had some limitations. The scoring system used in this analysis is limited in
20 that it may not reflect the true weight of adopting certain HWL measures. For example, a quitline
21 may have a greater impact on the prevalence of tobacco use than descriptive C&E message.
22 However, the scoring system does give additional weight to countries that have adopted
23 standardized packaging policies. An additional limitation is that the study analyzed only the
24 adoption of laws and not their implementation and enforcement. Finally, we included only
25 national laws, excluding sub-national laws such as the one adopted in Zanzibar, a semi-
26 autonomous region of the Republic of Tanzania.
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37 CONCLUSION

38 Most AFRO countries have adopted tobacco packaging and labeling policies that align
39 with Article 11 of the WHO FCTC and its Implementation Guidelines, specifically, regarding
40 rotating large pictorial HWLs, and banning misleading brand descriptors. More efforts could be
41 directed toward disseminating standardized packaging throughout AFRO.
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3 **DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT**
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6 The data underlying this article are available in the article and in its online supplementary
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8 material.
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13
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17
18 database.
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25 EMS, KD, CF, KW, BCB, MM, and EC have nothing to declare.
26

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41 **ETHICS APPROVAL**
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44 Not applicable for this study.
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FIGURES CAPTIONS

Figure 1: Health Warning Labels Size in AFRO, 1985-2023

Figure 2: Health Warning Labels Type in AFRO, 1985-2023

Figure 3: Health Warning Labels at least 50% and pictorial in AFRO, 1985-2023

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Figure 1. Health Warning Labels Size in AFRO, 1985-2023

279x215mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 2. Health Warning Labels Type in AFRO, 1985-2023

279x215mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Figure 3. Health Warning Labels at least 50% & pictorial in AFRO, 1985-2023

279x215mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Supplementary Table 1: Tobacco Health Warning Label Features, AFRO (December 2023)

COUNTRY	Tobacco product	Type	Location	Size		Rotation	Number	Message content	Principal language/s	Quit info
				% of PDAs	Average					
Algeria*	Smoked	Pictorial	Front	NS	N/A	NS	NS	General	NS	No
			Back	NS						
	Smokeless	Text-only	NS	NS	N/A	NS	NS	General	Arabic and French	
Angola	None	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Benin	All	Pictorial	Front	90	90	2 years	4	Lip cancer; mouth cancer; lung cancer; tongue cancer	French	No
				Back						
Botswana*	All	Pictorial	Front	70	70	NS	NS	NS	English or any other specified languages	No
				Back						
Burkina Faso	All	Pictorial	Front	60	60	1 year	1	Lung cancer; throat cancer	French and other principal national language	No
				Back						
Burundi	All	Pictorial	Front	50	50	NS	NS	NS	Kirundi and international languages recognized in matters of commerce	No
				Back						
Cabo Verde	Cigarettes	Pictorial	Front	50	75	NS	NS	NS	NS	No
				Back						
				Lateral	100					
Cameroon	All	Pictorial	Front	70	70	2 years	2	Lung cancer; death; rotten teeth; mouth cancer	French and English	No
				Back						
Central African Republic	All	Text-only	Lateral	NS		NR	1	General	French	No
Chad	All	Pictorial	Front	80	80	2 years	2	Mouth cancer; lung cancer; rotten teeth; pregnancy	French & Arabic	No
				Back						
Comoros	Smoked	Text-only	Front	40	40	NR	1	General	French and Comorian in Arabic letters	No
				Back						
	Smokeless	Text-only	Front	40	40	NR	1	General and addiction		
				Back						
Congo*	All	Pictorial	NS	At least 30		2 years	4	General	French and in the spoken languages	No

Cote d'Ivoire	All	Pictorial	Front	70	70	NS	NS	NS	French	No
			Back	70						
Democratic Republic of Congo	Cigarettes and cigars	Pictorial	Front	50	50	NR	NS	NS	NS	No
			Back	50						
Equatorial Guinea	None	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Eritrea*	All	Text-only	Front	30	30	NS	NS	NS	English	No
			Back	30						
Eswatini	All	Text-only	Front	50	50	NR	NS	General	NS	No
			Back	50						
Ethiopia	All	Pictorial	Front	70	70	2 years	4	Miscarriage; heart disease; oral cancer; lung cancer	Amharic and English (or another local language)	No
			Back	70						
Gabon	Smoked	Pictorial	Front	60	62.5	2 years	2	Lung cancer; mouth cancer; complications during pregnancy; impotence; death; breast cancer	French	No
			Back	65						
Gambia	Smoked	Pictorial	Front	81.5	81.5	2 years	NS	Impotence, miscarriage; lung disease; clogged arteries; heart attacks and strokes; cancer; death; addiction; harmful to children; aging; death; SIDS; skin cancer; infertility; poverty; pollution; bush fires; asthma	English	No
			Back	81.5						
Ghana	Smoked	Pictorial	Front	50	55	2 years	7	Heart attack; leg cancer; throat cancer; rotten teeth; unborn child; lung disease; secondhand smoke	English	Yes
			Back	60						
	Smokeless	Pictorial	Front	65	65					
			Back	65						
Guinea	All	Text-only	Front	30	30	NR	1	General	French	No
			Back	30						
Guinea Bissau	None	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Kenya	Smoked	Pictorial	Front	30	40	1 year	11	Secondhand smoke; death; cancer; lung disease; addiction; gum disease and tooth loss; mouth cancer; impotence; premature birth; infertility	English and Kiswahili	No
			Back	50						
	Smokeless	Pictorial	Front	30	40	1 year	6	Gum disease and tooth loss; mouth cancer; not safe alternative to cigarettes		
			Back	50						

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Lesotho	None	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Liberia	None	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Madagascar	Cigarettes & snuff	Pictorial	Front	50	50	1 year	4	Lung disease; death; mouth disease; secondhand smoke.	Malagasy	No	
		Text-only	Back	50							
	Chewing tobacco	Text-only	Front	0	25	1 year	2	Damages liver; lung damage; child health			
	Text-only	Back	50								
Malawi	None	N/A	N/A	N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Mali	All	Text-only	Front	30	30	NR	1	General	French	No	
			Back	30							
Mauritania	All tobacco products	Pictorial	Front	70	70	2 years	2	Lung cancer; rotted teeth	French and Arabic	No	
			Back	70							
		Text-only	Lateral	NS		NS	1	Quitting smoking			
Mauritius	Cigarettes and pipe tobacco	Pictorial	Front	80	90	1 year	8	Miscarriage, lung cancer, impotence and infertility, gangrene and amputation, premature aging, contains toxic substances	English and French	No	
			Back	100							
	Text-only	Laterals	70		NS	1	Death				
Mozambique	All	Text-only	Front	30	27.5	NR	NS	NS	Portuguese	No	
			Back	25							
Namibia	All	Pictorial	Front	50	55	NS	12	Secondhand smoke; death; lung disease; breast cancer; blindness and cataracts; rotten teeth; throat cancer; unborn baby; heart disease	English	No	
			Back	60							
Niger	Cigarettes & cigars	Pictorial	Front	50	50	2 years	2	Lung cancer; mouth cancer; pregnancy complications; harms to child health; impotence; secondhand smoke; death; breast cancer	French	No	
			Back	50							
Nigeria	All	Pictorial	Front	50	50	2 years	1	Lung cancer; mouth cancer; throat cancer	English	No	
			Back	50							

		Text-only	Lateral	NS			1	Death, quitting		
Rwanda	All	Text-only	Front	30	30	NR	1	Death; cancer, heart diseases; impotence; infertility; miscarriage; stroke	Kinyarwanda and English or French	No
			Back	30						
Sao Tome and Principe	All	Text-only	NS	NS		NR	NR	NS	Portuguese	No
Senegal	All	Pictorial	Front	70	70	1 year	1	Death; heart disease	French	Yes
			Back	70						
		Text-only	Laterals	NS			1 year	Impotence and sterility; damage to the health of those around you		
Seychelles	All	Pictorial	Front	50	50	NR	8	Harmful to children health; addiction; impotence; lung cancer; death; heart disease; mouth cancer; stroke	English, French, or Creole	No
			Back	50						
Sierra Leone	Smoked	Pictorial	Front	90	90	NR	13	Secondhand smoke; death; harms to unborn baby; miscarriages; cancer; heart, gum disease; addictive; impotence; infertility; mental retardation in children	English	No
			Back	90						
	Smokeless	Pictorial	Front	90						
			Back	90						
South Africa	Smoked	Text-only	Front	15	20	1 year	8	Death; cancer; heart disease; lungs; pregnancy and baby; children; addiction; secondhand smoke	One of the principal languages	No
			Back	25						
	Smokeless	Text-only	Front	15	7.5	NR	1	Cancer		
			Back	0						
South Sudan	None	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Togo	All & derivative products (e.g., e-cigarettes)	Text-only	Front	65	65	2 years	4	Addiction; children health; heart disease; stroke; lung cancer; mouth cancer; impotence; death; secondhand smoke; limbs amputation	French, Ewe, and Kabye	No
			Back	65						
Tanzania	Smoked	Text-only	Front	30	30	NR	10	Secondhand smoke; death; cancer; lung disease; heart & fatal diseases	Kiswahili and English	No
			Back	30						
Uganda	Smoked	Pictorial	Front	65	65	2 years	4	Lung cancer; heart attack; throat cancer; mouth cancer	English	No
			Back	65						
Zambia	All	Text-only	NS	NS		NR	1	General	NS	No
Zimbabwe	Smoked	Text-only	NS	NS		NR	NR	General	NS	No

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	Smokeless	Text-only	NS	NS			Addiction; cancer		
NS: Not specified NR: Not required *Regulations are pending									

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Supplementary Table 2: Descriptive Constituents & Emissions Information (December 2023)							
COUNTRY	Type of product	Type	Size	Location	Rotation	Number	Message content
Algeria*	Uncertain	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Angola	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Benin	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Botswana	All tobacco products	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Burkina Faso	All tobacco products	Text-only	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Burundi	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Cabo Verde	Uncertain	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Cameroon	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Central African Republic	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Chad	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Comoros	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Congo*	Uncertain	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Cote d'Ivoire	Uncertain	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Democratic Republic of Congo	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Equatorial Guinea	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Eritrea*	Uncertain	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Eswatini	All tobacco products	Text-only	NS	Lateral	NS	NS	Tar, nicotine, other constituents (NS)

Ethiopia	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Gabon	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Gambia	All tobacco products	Text-only	NS	Lateral	Two years	NS	NS
Ghana	All tobacco products	NS	NS	Lateral	NS	3	Nicotine is addictive; carbon monoxide affects breathing; arsenic causes cancers of the lung, skin, bladder, liver and kidney
Guinea	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Guinea Bissau	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Kenya	All tobacco products	Text-only	NS	Lateral	NS	NS	Tar, nicotine, other constituents (NS)
Lesotho	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Liberia	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Madagascar	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Malawi	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Mali	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Mauritania	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Mauritius	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Mozambique	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Namibia	All tobacco products	Text-only	NS	NS	NS	NS	Tar, nicotine, other harmful chemicals (NS)
Niger	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Nigeria	All tobacco products	Text-only	NS	Lateral	NS	1	Tobacco smoke contains over 70 substances known to cause cancer
Rwanda	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Sao Tome and Principe	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Senegal	All tobacco products	Text-only	NS	Lateral	NS	NS	NS
Seychelles	All tobacco products	Text-only	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Sierra Leone	Smoked tobacco products	Text-only	NS	NS	NS	NS	Tobacco smoke contains over 70 substances known to cause cancer
South Africa	Smoked tobacco products ¹	Text-only	25%	Back	N/A	1	Carbon monoxide, cyanide, nicotine, tar
South Sudan	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Tanzania	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Togo	Cigarettes	Text-only	NS	Lateral	NS	2	Benzene; 60 chemical products that can cause cancer
Uganda	All tobacco products	Text-only	100%	Top	NS	1	Tobacco smoke contains over 70 substances known to cause cancer
Zambia	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Zimbabwe	Not required	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
<p>1: Not required on every package, but only as 1 of the 8 HWLs *Regulations are pending; N/A: Not applicable; NS: Not specified</p>							

Supplementary Table 3: Misleading Tobacco Packaging and Labeling (December 2023)

COUNTRY	Type of product	Brand descriptors	Emission yields	Figures, colors and other signs	Expiry date	Plain/ Standardized packaging
Algeria	All tobacco products	Allowed	Required	Allowed	Allowed	No
Angola	Not required	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	No
Benin	All tobacco products	Banned	Allowed	Banned	Allowed	No
Botswana	All tobacco products	Banned	Banned	Banned	Allowed	No
Burkina Faso	All tobacco products	Banned	Allowed	Banned	Allowed	No
Burundi	All tobacco products	Banned	Required	Banned	Allowed	No
Cabo Verde	All tobacco products	Banned	Uncertain	Banned	Allowed	No
Cameroon	All tobacco products	Banned	Banned	Banned	Required	No
Central African Republic	Not required	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	No
Chad	All tobacco products	Banned	Allowed	Banned	Allowed	No
Comoros	All tobacco products	Banned	Required	Banned	Allowed	No
Congo	All tobacco products	Banned	Banned	Allowed	Allowed	No
Cote d'Ivoire	Not required	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Yes
Democratic Republic of Congo	Cigarettes and cigars	Banned	Required	Allowed	Required	No
Equatorial Guinea	Not required	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	No
Eritrea	All tobacco products	Banned	Allowed	Banned	Allowed	No
Eswatini	All tobacco products	Banned	Banned	Banned	Allowed	No

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Ethiopia	All tobacco products	Banned	Banned	Banned	Banned	No
Gabon	All tobacco products	Allowed	Required	Allowed	Required	No
Gambia	All Tobacco products	Banned	Banned	Banned	Allowed	No
Ghana	All tobacco products	Banned	Banned	Banned	Allowed	No
Guinea	All tobacco products	Banned	Required	Banned	Allowed	No
Guinea Bissau	Not required	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	No
Kenya	All tobacco products	Banned	Banned	Banned	Allowed	No
Lesotho	Not required	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	No
Liberia	Not required	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	No
Madagascar	All tobacco products	Banned	Allowed	Banned	Allowed	No
Malawi	All tobacco products	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Required	No
Mali	All tobacco products	Banned	Required	Allowed	Allowed	No
Mauritania	All tobacco products	Banned	Banned	Banned	Banned	No
Mauritius	All tobacco products	Banned	Banned	Banned	Allowed	Yes
Mozambique	All tobacco products	Allowed	Allowed	Banned	Allowed	No
Namibia	All tobacco products	Banned	Required	Banned	Allowed	No
Niger	All tobacco products	Banned	Required	Banned	Required	No
Nigeria	All tobacco products	Banned	Banned	Banned	Required	No
Rwanda	All tobacco products	Banned	Required	Allowed	Allowed	No
Sao Tome and Principe	Not required	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	No

Senegal	All tobacco products	Banned	Banned	Banned	Allowed	No
Seychelles	All tobacco products	Banned	Allowed	Banned	Allowed	No
Sierra Leone	All tobacco products	Banned	Allowed	Banned	Allowed	No
South Africa	All tobacco products	Banned	Required	Banned	Allowed	No
South Sudan	Not required	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	No
Tanzania	All tobacco products	Banned	Required	Banned	Allowed	No
Togo	All tobacco products	Banned	Banned	Allowed	Allowed	No
Uganda	All tobacco products	Banned	Banned	Banned	Allowed	No
Zambia	Not required	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	No
Zimbabwe	Not required	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	Allowed	No

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**Supplementary Table 4:
Scoring of AFRO countries by WB income level based on the level of adoption of
WHO FCTC's Article 11 requirements and recommendations (December 2023)**

World Bank income level	COUNTRY	Health Warning Labels (max: 16)									Constituents & Emissions Information (max: 4)		Misleading Packaging & Labeling (max: 10)					Total score (max: 30)
		Type (2)	Location (2)	Size (3)	Rotation length (2)	Number of warnings (2)	In principal language (2)	Message content (2)	Quit information (1)	Message content (2)	Rotation length (2)	Ban on brand descriptors (2)	Ban on emission yields (1)	Ban on figures, colors, and symbols (2)	Ban on expiry date (1)	Plain packaging (max: 4)		
High	Seychelles	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	0	1	1	2	0	2	0	0	18	
Upper-Middle	Mauritius	2	2	3	2	2	2	2	0	0	0	2	1	2	0	4	24	
	Namibia	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	0	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	19	
	South Africa	1	2	0	0	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	17	
	Gabon	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	16	
	Botswana	2	2	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	1	2	0	0	13	
	Equatorial Guinea	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Lower-Middle	Ghana	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	0	0	23	
	Kenya	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	0	2	1	2	1	2	0	0	21	
	Senegal	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	0	0	21	
	Cameroon	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	0	2	1	2	0	0	19	
	Mauritania	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	2	1	2	1	0	18	
	Nigeria	1	2	1	0	1	2	2	0	2	1	2	1	2	0	0	17	
	Eswatini	1	2	2	0	0	0	2	0	2	1	2	1	2	0	0	15	
	Benin	2	2	3	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	15	
	Tanzania	1	2	1	0	2	2	2	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	14	
	Comoros	1	2	1	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	12	
	Congo	2	0	1	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	12	
	Cabo Verde	2	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	11	
	Cote d'Ivoire	2	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	11	
	Guinea	1	2	1	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	11	
	Zimbabwe	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	
	Zambia	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	
Angola	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Lesotho	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		

Low	Uganda	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	1	2	1	2	0	0	22
	Gambia	2	2	3	2	0	2	2	0	1	2	2	1	2	0	0	21	
	Chad	2	2	3	2	2	2	2	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	19	
	Sierra Leone	2	2	3	0	2	2	2	0	2	0	2	0	2	0	0	19	
	Togo	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	1	2	1	0	0	0	19	
	Burkina Faso	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	0	1	1	2	0	2	0	0	18	
	Madagascar	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	18	
	Ethiopia	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	2	1	2	1	0	18	
	Niger	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	18	
	Burundi	2	2	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	12	
	Mali	1	2	1	2	1	2	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	11	
	Rwanda	1	2	1	0	1	2	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	11	
	Eritrea	1	2	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	10	
	Mozambique	1	2	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	10	
	Democratic Republic of Congo	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	7	
	Central African Republic	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	
	Malawi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	
	Guinea-Bissau	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Liberia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
South Sudan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		

AFRO: World Health Organization African Region
WB: World Bank
WHO FCTC: World Health Organization Framework Convention on Tobacco Control

Scoring system:**1) Health warning labels:**

Type (text-only [1 point] or pictorial [2 points]), location (lateral only [1 point] or front and back [2 points]), size (as a percentage of the PDA of the pack [less than 30% [0 points], 30% to 49% [1 point], 50% to 69% [2 points], and 70% or more [3 points]), rotation period (not required [0 points] required but not specified [1 point], required and specified [2 points]), number (not specified or not required [0 points], 1 message [1 point], 2+ messages [2 points]), principal language/s (not specified or none [0 points], messages required to appear in one or more principal languages [2 points]), message content areas (general, not specified or not required [0 points], 1 content area [1 point], 2+ content areas [2 points]), and quit resource information (not required or specified [0 points], required [1 point]).

2) Descriptive constituents & emissions information:

Message content (not required [0 points], 1 message required but not specified [1 point], 1+ messages required and specified [2 points]), rotation period (not required or N/A [0 points], required but not specified [1 point], required and specified [2 points]).

3) Misleading packaging & labeling:

Ban on brand descriptors (allowed [0 points], partial ban [1 point], full ban [2 points]), ban on emission yields (allowed or required [0 points], full ban [1 point]), ban on figures, colors, and symbols (allowed [0 points], banned [2 points]), ban on expiry date (allowed or required [0 points], full ban [1 point]), plain packaging (not required [0 points], required [4 points]).

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For Peer Review

**Supplementary Table 5:
Ranking of AFRO countries by WB income level based on the level of adoption of
WHO FCTC's Article 11 requirements and recommendations (December 2023)**

World Bank Income Level	Country	Total score (max: 30) *	Cumulative score by income-level group	Maximum possible cumulative score by income-level group (30 points X # of countries)	% of maximum possible score earned (cumulative score/ maximum possible cumulative score X 100)
High	Seychelles	18	18	30	60%
Upper-Middle	Mauritius	24	89	180	49%
	Namibia	19			
	South Africa	17			
	Gabon	16			
	Botswana	13			
	Equatorial Guinea	0			
Lower-Middle	Ghana	23	225	540	42%
	Kenya	21			
	Senegal	21			
	Cameroon	19			
	Mauritania	18			
	Nigeria	17			
	Eswatini	15			
	Benin	15			
	Tanzania	14			
	Comoros	12			
	Congo	12			
	Cabo Verde	11			
	Cote d'Ivoire	11			
	Guinea	11			
Zimbabwe	3				

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	Zambia	2			
	Angola	0			
	Lesotho	0			
	Uganda	22	236	600	39%
	Gambia	21			
	Chad	19			
	Sierra Leone	19			
	Togo	19			
	Burkina Faso	18			
	Madagascar	18			
	Ethiopia	18			
	Niger	18			
	Burundi	12			
	Mali	11			
	Rwanda	11			
	Eritrea	10			
	Mozambique	10			
	Democratic Republic of Congo	7			
	Central African Republic	2			
	Malawi	1			
	Guinea-Bissau	0			
	Liberia	0			
	South Sudan	0			
Low					
AFRO: World Health Organization African Region WB: World Bank WHO FCTC: World Health Organization Framework Convention on Tobacco Control * Note: See table 4 for detailed breakdown					

**Supplementary Table 6:
Ranking of AFRO countries based on the compliance with WHO FCTC's
Article 11 requirements and recommendations (December 2023)**

Country	Health warning labels (max: 16)								Constituents & emissions information (max: 4)		Misleading packaging & labeling (max: 10)					Total compliance points (max: 15)
	Type (2)	Location (2)	Size (3)	Rotation length (2)	Number of warnings (2)	In principal language (2)	Message content (2)	Quit information (1)	Message content (2)	Rotation length (2)	Ban on brand descriptors (2)	Ban on emission yields (1)	Ban on figures, colors, and symbols (2)	Ban on expiry date (1)	Plain packaging (max: 4)	
Ghana																13
Senegal																12
Uganda																12
Gambia																11
Kenya																11
Mauritius																11
Burkina Faso																10
Cameroon																10
Ethiopia																10
Mauritania																10
Namibia																10
Seychelles																10
Togo																10
Madagascar																9
Niger																9
Sierra Leone																9
South Africa																9
Chad																8
Eswatini																8
Gabon																8
Nigeria																8
Benin																7

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Botswana	Green	Green	Green			Green						Green	Green	Green			7
Burundi	Green	Green	Green			Green						Green		Green			6
Congo	Green			Green	Green	Green						Green	Green				6
Tanzania		Green			Green	Green	Green					Green		Green			6
Cabo Verde	Green	Green	Green									Green		Green			5
Comoros		Green			Green	Green						Green		Green			5
Cote d'Ivoire	Green	Green	Green													Green	4
Democratic Republic of Congo	Green	Green	Green									Green					4
Eritrea		Green				Green						Green		Green			4
Guinea		Green				Green						Green		Green			4
Mali		Green		Green		Green						Green					4
Mozambique		Green				Green						Green		Green			4
Rwanda		Green				Green	Green					Green					4
Malawi											Green						1
Zimbabwe		Green															1
Angola																	0
Central African Republic																	0
Equatorial Guinea																	0
Guinea-Bissau																	0
Lesotho																	0
Liberia																	0
South Sudan																	0
Zambia																	0
AFRO: World Health Organization African Region WHO FCTC: World Health Organization Framework Convention on Tobacco Control																	

Compliance status:

Each AFRO country receives one point (noted in green in the table) if in compliance with each one of the 15 characteristics based on the requirements and recommendations of WHO FCTC Article 11 and its Implementation Guidelines. A country could achieve a maximum of 15 points.

